

Inelastic Shear Buckling Curves for Flat Stiffened Glare Panels

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SUMMARY: The present paper discusses an analysis procedure for shear buckling of flat, stiffened Glare panels in the inelastic range. This procedure assumes that the skin material of the panels is isotropic. Since Glare is actually an orthotropic material due to the arrangement of the glass fibres, it is shown for a specific example that the calculated plastic buckling stresses are about 6% unconservative with respect to results for which the skin orthotropy is fully retained. However, the isotropic procedure is much faster since it employs readily available solutions for shear buckling, which were generated previously, whereas the orthotropic analysis is done with relatively large Finite Element Method models, requiring a lot of computational effort for the iterative calculation procedure. Furthermore, it is demonstrated that the plasticity correction factor, which is the ratio of the plastic and elastic buckling stress and is commonly used for design purposes, is only a function of the buckling stress based on purely elastic behaviour, independent of the actual panel configuration. Curves relating the plasticity correction factor to the elastic shear buckling stress are presented for a number of Glare 3 materials with different aluminium content, and can be conveniently used in the buckling design of stiffened Glare shear panels.

KEYWORDS: Shear Buckling, Stiffened Panels, Plasticity, Glare, Design.

INTRODUCTION

Glare is a commercially available Fibre Metal Laminate (FML) that consists of alternate aluminium sheets and high-strength glass fibre pre-impregnated layers. The excellent fatigue characteristics, combined with a lower density than aluminium due to the presence of the lighter fibre layers, and additionally some other favourable characteristics such as fire resistance, make Glare attractive as fuselage skin material in future Ultra-High Capacity Aircraft (UHCA), such as the all new Airbus A380 [1]. Glare is commercially available in different grades, which differ by composition of the glass fibre layers (e.g. unidirectional, cross-ply, or angle-ply lay-ups), see Ref. [1].

In conventional fuselage design, it is practice to exploit the post-buckling behaviour of stiffened panels loaded in shear for the obvious weight saving potential. A requirement, however, to operate in the post-buckling region is that the panel is of thin gauge, so that the initial buckling mode is local; this allows for the stiffening elements to serve as compression posts to counterbalance the diagonal tension stresses which develop in the skin when the shear load is increased further beyond the critical point. This particular mechanism causes the eventual failure load to be (sometimes much) higher than the initial buckling load. However, the skin thickness associated with an UHCA fuselage panel is relatively large since this quantity is roughly speaking proportional to the fuselage diameter. An increasing skin thickness essentially has two effects on the buckling behaviour of a stiffened shear panel. First, the stiffeners get weaker in effectively supporting the skin, so that at a certain point the initial buckling mode shifts from a local to an overall-type pattern. The second effect is a rapid increase in the value of the buckling stress—which is proportional to the thickness squared—so that buckling is prone to occur in the plastic region.

Shear buckling of flat, unstiffened Glare plates in the inelastic region has been studied previously by the authors using different elasto-plastic models [2-4]. In Ref. [2] a tentative approach is described that is based on Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) and the shear secant modulus of the aluminium layers. This procedure was demonstrated through calculation of plastic buckling loads for some Glare

configurations. Results from this CLT-based procedure proved to be generally conservative with respect to the “classical” design method for fully metallic plates [3], which assumes that the plates are homogenous and isotropic. In Ref. [4] the J2-deformation plasticity theory is employed for the aluminium layers in conjunction with CLT, producing slightly lower buckling loads compared to the method based on the shear secant modulus of the aluminium layers. Since it produces the most conservative results, it was concluded that the deformation theory approach should be used for design purposes in absence of suitable experimental data. Inelastic buckling loads obtained from non-linear Finite Element Method (FEM) analyses, including small initial plate imperfections and employing the J2-flow plasticity theory, showed a fair agreement with the CLT-based procedures, both with deformation theory and the shear secant modulus method.

The calculation procedure for the plastic buckling load utilising J2-deformation theory was extended to stiffened panels in Ref. [5]. While for the unstiffened plates the actual buckling analyses were performed with (semi-)analytical methods yielding fast results, the FEM method was employed in Ref. [5] for the analysis of the stiffened panels. Because the calculation procedure for the inelastic buckling load requires small load increments, at each of which a buckling analysis must be performed, the use of FEM models requires a lot of computational effort. Since the purpose of Ref. [5] was to demonstrate the calculation procedure rather than to generate accurate results, a relatively small and coarse FEM model was employed to speed up analysis time.

In the present paper, inelastic buckling loads of stiffened Glare shear panels are calculated using more accurate FEM models. In addition, results are shown for aluminium panels for reference purposes. The analysis is done by employing the elastic shear buckling results generated in Ref. [6], which are essentially only valid for panels having isotropic skin material. Since Glare is an orthotropic material due to the fibre arrangement, an error is introduced when using this isotropic approach. To assess the magnitude of this error, plastic buckling loads calculated from the isotropic method are compared to results where the orthotropy of the skin material is fully retained. Finally, design curves relating the plasticity correction factor, which is the ratio of the plastic and elastic buckling stress to the elastic buckling stress, are presented for panels made of Glare 3 material, which has an equal amount of fibres in the two principal material directions.

ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

Elastic shear buckling of stiffened Glare panels

The present study considers a simply-supported infinitely long panel with transverse stiffeners subjected to pure shear loading, such as shown schematically in Fig. 1. The stiffeners are assumed to possess flexural stiffness only, and the skin material of the panel is assumed to be isotropic. For such a panel, the shear buckling stress can be given by the formula [7,8]

$$\tau_{cr} = K_s \frac{\pi^2 D}{b^2 t} \quad (1)$$

where b is the stiffener spacing, t is the thickness, and D is the bending stiffness of the plate. The non-dimensional shear buckling coefficient K_s is a function of the following two non-dimensional panel parameters:

$$\alpha = \frac{a}{b} \quad (2)$$

$$\mu_F = \frac{EI}{Db} \quad (3)$$

which are the aspect ratio of the individual skin bays and the stiffener flexural stiffness parameter, respectively. In these parameters, a is the length of the skin bays (i.e. depth of the panel), and EI is the

flexural stiffness of the stiffeners. The parameter μ_F is a measure of the relative flexural stiffness of the stiffener with respect to the bending stiffness of the skin; a high value forces the individual skin bays to buckle between the stringers (local buckling), whereas a low value represents weak stiffeners that buckle along with the skin (overall buckling), see Fig. 2.

Curves relating K_s to α and μ_F have been derived in Refs. [7,8] using the Rayleigh-Ritz method, where it should be noted that a slightly different definition of K_s was used; instead of the stiffener pitch b , the panel depth a was used in the denominator of Eq. (1). In Ref. [6], non-dimensional shear buckling curves as defined by Eq. (1) were derived using the STAGS [9] FEM code, and the results are shown in Fig. 3. They were calculated using models with 10 stiffeners with all edges simply-supported, which may be regarded as equivalent to an infinite panel since a further increase in the number of stiffeners causes no significant decrease in buckling load. This is except for the really (uninterestingly) low values of μ_F , for which the panel behaves more or less like an unstiffened panel (i.e. where $\mu_F = 0$) and the simply-supported boundary conditions at the short edges have an influence on the buckling load. Note that in Fig. 3 the quantity $\sqrt{\mu_F}$ is used rather than μ_F since this is more convenient for plotting purposes.

Fig. 1: Infinitely long panel with transverse stiffeners loaded in shear.

Fig. 2: Different buckling modes for (a) weak stiffeners, and (b) strong stiffeners.

Fig. 3: Shear buckling coefficient of Eq. (1) as a function of the aspect ratio and flexural stiffness parameter for an infinitely long panel (graph taken from Ref [6]).

The curves in Fig. 3 can be approximated fairly accurately with the following formula [6]:

$$K_s(\alpha, \mu_F) = 6.19 - \frac{19.84}{\alpha^3} - \frac{8.05}{\alpha^2} + \frac{27.47}{\alpha} + 3.48 \frac{\hat{\mu}_F}{\alpha^2} + 19.73 \frac{\hat{\mu}_F}{\alpha} - 6.58 \frac{\hat{\mu}_F^2}{\alpha} - 0.38 \hat{\mu}_F - 3.35 \hat{\mu}_F^2 - 8.74 \hat{\mu}_F^3 \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\mu}_F = \ln \sqrt{\mu_F}$, which may be conveniently used for design purposes. The quantity $\mu_{F,cr}$ marks the transition point from an overall to a local buckling mode, after which a further increase of stiffener rigidity has no effect on the buckling load. This critical flexural stiffness parameter can be calculated from the expression

$$\sqrt{\mu_{F,cr}} = 0.29\alpha^3 - 2.04\alpha^2 + 11.02\alpha - 2.34 \quad (5)$$

and is an important design parameter.

Essentially, the solution for the shear buckling stress presented above is only valid for panels having isotropic skin material with a unique bending stiffness D . Since Glare material is orthotropic as a result of the arrangement of the glass fibre layers, a tentative “equivalent” bending stiffness is introduced as [5,6]

$$D \rightarrow D_{eq} = \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} \quad (6)$$

where D_{11} and D_{22} are the bending stiffnesses in the principle material directions; the 1-direction is assumed parallel to the stiffeners, the 2-direction perpendicular to the stiffeners. This equivalent bending stiffness now replaces the quantity D in Eqs. (1) and (3) while retaining the “isotropic” shear buckling coefficient plotted in Fig. 3. Results from this approach tend to be within 5 to 10% unconservative compared to the solutions where the orthotropic behaviour of the skin material is fully accounted for, depending on the fibre arrangement (i.e. Glare grade) [5].

Calculation procedure for the plastic shear buckling stress

When the stresses in the aluminium layers exceed the proportional limit, the effective stiffness of the Glare material decreases and, consequently, so does the buckling stress. Since the panel is subjected to pure shear loading, there is also a state of pure shear stress in the individual aluminium layers. In this case, the incremental stiffness matrix of the aluminium layers according to J2-deformation theory can be obtained from, for example, Refs. [10] and [11], and is given here explicitly as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\sigma}_{11} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{22} \\ \dot{\sigma}_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_s}{1-\nu_s^2} & \frac{\nu_s E_s}{1-\nu_s^2} \\ \frac{\nu_s E_s}{1-\nu_s^2} & \frac{E_s}{1-\nu_s^2} \\ \frac{E_s}{2(1+\nu_s)} \left[1 - \frac{E_s/E_t - 1}{E_s/E_t - (1-2\nu_s)/3} \right] & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{11} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{22} \\ 2\dot{\epsilon}_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

with

$$\frac{\nu_s}{E_s} = \frac{\nu}{E} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{E_s} - \frac{1}{E} \right] \quad (8)$$

where E , E_s , and E_t are the elastic, secant, and tangent modulus of the applied aluminium, respectively. Furthermore, $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ are the incremental tensorial stresses and $\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}$ the incremental tensorial strains. The dependence of the stiffness matrix in Eq. (7) on the stress level is reflected in the secant and tangent

modulus. Using a Ramberg-Osgood representation for the elasto-plastic behaviour of aluminium of the following type

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sigma_M}{E} + \alpha \frac{\sigma_y}{E} \left(\frac{\sigma_M}{\sigma_y} \right)^n, \quad \alpha = \frac{0.002E}{\sigma_y} \quad (9)$$

the secant and tangent modulus can be calculated from

$$E_s = E \left[1 + \alpha \left(\frac{\sigma_M}{\sigma_y} \right)^{n-1} \right]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

$$E_t = E \left[1 + \alpha n \left(\frac{\sigma_M}{\sigma_y} \right)^{n-1} \right]^{-1} \quad (11)$$

In these expressions, ε is the strain, E is the elastic (Young's) modulus, σ_y is the uniaxial yield stress, n is the strain hardening parameter, and σ_M is the Von Mises equivalent stress given by

$$\sigma_M = \sqrt{\sigma_{11}^2 + \sigma_{22}^2 - \sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + 3\sigma_{12}^2} \quad (12)$$

which reduces to the simple form $\sigma_M = \sqrt{3}\sigma_{12}$ for pure shear loading. Note that the glass fibre layers in Glare are assumed to behave linearly elastic at all stress levels.

The problem in establishing the correct buckling stress is that the bending stiffness terms D_{ij} , which are used in the buckling analysis [see Eqs. (1) and (6)], depend on the stress level. The buckling load therefore has to be solved in an iterative manner. Small incremental steps are taken along the stress-strain path and for each point a buckling analysis is performed. The following iterative solution procedure is now employed:

1. Choose a step size for the applied shear load. (Typical stress level of 1/1000 times the yield stress);
2. Calculate the laminate membrane stiffnesses (A-matrix) using Classical Laminate Theory and J2-deformation theory incremental moduli for the aluminium layers [Eqs. (7) through (12)];
3. Calculate the incremental shear strain from the inverse of the A-matrix;
4. Calculate the aluminium layer incremental shear stress from the incremental strains using Eq. (7), and subsequently calculate the total shear stress;
5. Calculate the D-matrix for the entire laminate using Classical Laminate Theory and J2-deformation theory incremental moduli corresponding to the current total stress level in the aluminium layers;
6. Calculate the shear buckling stress for this laminate from Eq. (1) or a FEM model;
7. Check whether the buckling stress is higher or lower than the applied shear stress:
 - if the buckling stress is higher, increase the load and continue at step 2;
 - else, if the buckling stress is lower, the solution is found.

Note that the analysis procedure above is based on in-plane loading conditions, so that each aluminium layer experiences the same stresses and strains and hence has the same stiffness properties at all stress levels. Once the plastic buckling stress has been obtained, the plasticity correction factor can be calculated as

$$\eta = \frac{\tau_{cr}}{\tau_{cr}^{(elastic)}} \quad (13)$$

where $\tau_{cr}^{(elastic)}$ is the shear buckling stress based on pure elastic behaviour of the aluminium layers. This reduction factor is commonly used for design purposes.

RESULTS

Accuracy of the isotropic approach

The calculation procedure presented in the previous section was demonstrated in Ref. [5], where the buckling analyses were performed with the STAGS FEM code. Since, for accuracy, the calculation method typically requires very small load increments, at each of which a buckling analysis must be performed, this process requires a lot of computing time. Therefore, in Ref. [5] a rather small (4 stiffeners) and coarse FEM model was used to speed up analysis time; this was no problem since the purpose was to demonstrate the calculation procedure rather than to generate accurate results.

A much faster way of doing the buckling analyses is to use the curves presented in Fig. 3, either by the formula of Eq. (4) or by interpolation of the data from which the curves are plotted. In this way, a single buckling solution is “immediately” available and the calculation of the inelastic buckling load is done in a matter of seconds. As mentioned earlier the curves in Fig. 3 are only valid for panels having isotropic skin material, and since Glare is orthotropic, an error is introduced in the buckling load even when the concept of equivalent bending stiffness [Eq. (6)] is used. To assess the level of this error, a number of analyses were made for a specific example panel configuration using both FEM (orthotropy of Glare retained) and the isotropic approach. The FEM models were the same as those with which the curves in Fig. 3 were generated (i.e. with 10 stiffeners and simply-supported boundary conditions at all edges); the results using the isotropic approach were obtained through linear interpolation of tabulated data. Calculations were made for a panel with $b = 125$ mm and an aspect ratio of $\alpha = 5$ for aluminium 2024-T3 alloy and Glare 3-5/4-0.4, with a thickness of $t = 3$ and 3.016 mm, respectively. The stacking sequence of the Glare 3 material is

$$[Al(0)/Gl(0)/Gl(90)/Al(0)/Gl(0)/Gl(90)/Al(0)/Gl(90)/Gl(0)/Al(0)/Gl(90)/Gl(0)/Al(0)]$$

where Al denotes an aluminium layer and Gl a unidirectional (UD) glass fibre ply, and the number in parentheses is the corresponding orientation, where the 0°-direction is parallel to the stiffeners. The aluminium layers have a thickness of 0.4 mm, the glass fibre plies a thickness of 0.127 mm. Material properties used for the aluminium and glass fibre prepreg layers are presented in Table 1. Note that the stiffness of the adhesive in the glass fibre plies is negligible [1], so that only a value for E_{11} (in the fibre direction) is used in the analysis and the other ply stiffnesses are set to zero. The properties of the aluminium layers are typical values for 2024-T3 alloy. The results for the shear buckling stresses are plotted in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 as a function of the stiffener rigidity EI for aluminium and Glare 3 material, respectively.

Table 1: Material properties used for the glass fibre and aluminium layers.

	Glass prepreg (UD)	2024-T3	
G	0	27218	MPa
ν	0.33	0.33	
E_{11}	52000	72400	MPa
E_{22}	0	72400	MPa
σ_y	-	290	MPa
n	-	10	

For the aluminium panel the elastic buckling results are the same for both methods, which should obviously be expected. However, there is a difference in the shear buckling stresses in the inelastic range. The explanation for this phenomenon is that, when the stresses in the aluminium exceed the proportional limit, the material loses its isotropy and, instead, becomes orthotropic due to a change in the stiffness matrix as indicated by Eq. (7). The difference between the isotropic and orthotropic analyses is already apparent in the elastic range for the Glare panel, which is logical since Glare is, by its nature, an orthotropic material. An increasing difference of results can be detected for increasing stiffener rigidity, with a constant maximum occurring for the case of local buckling. This may be explained by the fact that for lower values of EI the stiffeners act more or less of they are “smeared out”, and therefore contribute relatively more to the orthotropy of the panel than the Glare skin material. For both the aluminium and Glare panel, the plastic (local) buckling stresses from the isotropic approach, using the concept of equivalent bending stiffness, are about 6% unconservative with respect to the orthotropic solution. Further, from Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 it can be seen that the transition point from an overall to a local buckling mode shifts to lower values of the stiffener rigidity, which is due to the increased flexibility of the skin material in the plastic range. This effect causes the stiffeners to become relatively stronger. The effect of plasticity for the Glare panel is more pronounced than for the aluminium panel, which is due to the lower metal content and the fibre arrangement: when loaded in pure shear, the fibres are not stressed so that the entire load is carried by the aluminium layers, resulting in a lower shear yield stress of the Glare material. It should be noted that it took about 6 to 7 hours to generate a single curve with the FEM analyses on a 2.4 GHz Pentium IV PC, whereas the method using the results of Fig. 3 calculated a single curve within a minute.

Fig. 4: Shear buckling stresses for the aluminium example panel from orthotropic and isotropic analysis.

Fig. 5: Shear buckling stresses for the Glare example panel from orthotropic and isotropic analysis.

Calculation of plasticity correction factors

In design practice it is customary to use a plasticity correction factor, η , as defined by Eq. (13), which essentially serves as a knockdown factor for the elastic buckling stress. Such factors were calculated using the isotropic approach for Al 2024-T3 alloy and Glare 3-5/4-0.4, and the results are plotted against the elastic buckling stress in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, respectively. In these calculations, a low and high aspect ratio was used ($\alpha = 1$ and 5) in combination with low, moderate, and high values of the stiffness parameter ($\mu_F = 1, 5$, and 40 for $\alpha = 1$, and $\mu_F = 50, 400$, and 1000 for $\alpha = 5$). The results show that almost all combinations of aspect ratio and stiffness parameter produce more or less the same plasticity correction factors. In fact, for the higher values of μ_F , where the condition of local buckling is in effect, the results are exactly the same for the high and low aspect ratio, for both the aluminium and Glare panels. This essentially implies that the plasticity correction factor is only a function of the value of the elastic buckling stress, independent of the aspect ratio and stiffness parameter. From Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 it can be seen that the panel with $\alpha = 5$ and $\mu_F = 50$ shows somewhat higher values for η . This may be explained by the fact that for low values of μ_F the

stiffeners behave as if they are “smeared out”, which essentially means that the panel acts as if it were made out of a different material. For a high aspect ratio, the stiffeners are spaced relatively closer so that the smearing-out effect is more pronounced. This explains why the different plastic buckling behaviour is only found for the panel with $\alpha = 5$ and not for the one with $\alpha = 1$. It can be shown that for a panel with $\mu_F = 0$ (i.e. an unstiffened plate) the same values for η are found as for the local buckling results presented in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, which means that the effect of stiffener smear-out is confined to a limited range of low stiffness parameters.

The results according to the orthotropic analysis that were obtained in the previous section (i.e. employing FEM buckling analysis) are also presented in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. It shows that the curves from the isotropic analysis agree quite well with the correction factors calculated with orthotropic analysis and are slightly on the unconservative side, which could have been expected considering the discussion of the previous section. This unconservatism seems to increase when the panel buckles further into the plastic region. Also plotted in Fig. 7 is the result for a Glare 3-5/4-0.4 test panel obtained from fully non-linear FEM analysis with STAGS as described in Ref. [12]. The experimental buckling load of this panel was shown to be virtually equal to the FEM result, so that the STAGS result may be considered reliable. The experimental/FEM result is shown to be in quite good agreement with the curves in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6: Plasticity correction factors for aluminium panels calculated from isotropic analysis using different aspect ratios and stiffness parameters.

Fig. 7: Plasticity correction factors for Glare panels calculated from isotropic analysis using different aspect ratios and stiffness parameters.

DESIGN CURVES

In the previous section it was discussed that the plasticity correction factor only depends on the value of the elastic buckling stress. However, since Glare is available in different configurations, the aluminium content—which governs the elasto-plastic behaviour of the laminate—will generally be different for each individual configuration. Consequently, there is no unique curve relating η to the elastic shear buckling stress for Glare panels, as is the case for aluminium or other metallic panels. In this context, an important parameter for Glare material is the so-called *metal volume fraction*, which is defined as

$$MVF = \frac{\text{total thickness of aluminium layers}}{\text{total laminate thickness}} \quad (14)$$

and is a measure for the aluminium content. For example, the Glare 3-5/4-0.4 material that was used in the previous section has a metal volume fraction of $MVF = (5 \times 0.4) / 3.016 = 0.66$. Fig. 8 shows different curves for the plasticity correction factor for Glare 3 configurations according to different values of MVF . From the results it is clear that the plasticity effect is the least for the Glare configurations with the higher metal content. This is to be expected, since the shear yield stress is more or less proportional to the metal volume fraction since the fibres are not stressed in a case of

pure shear loading. In the far-plastic range, the laminate stiffness is almost entirely governed by the elastic glass fibre layers, which is reflected by the horizontal slope of the curve corresponding to $MVF = 0.48$.

The curves in Fig. 8 can now be conveniently used for the shear buckling design of stiffened Glare 3 panels. First, the elastic shear buckling stress is calculated using Eqs. (1) through (3) and (6), in conjunction with Fig. 3 or Eq. (4), after which the plasticity correction factor and hence the plastic buckling load is readily obtained from Fig. 8. The value of μ_F in Eq. (3) is calculated for elastic properties of the equivalent bending stiffness D_{eq} . As the shear buckling stress advances into the plastic region, the value of D_{eq} drops so that the effective stiffness parameter increases. The elastic value of μ_F is related to the effective value as

$$\frac{\mu_F^{(elastic)}}{\mu_F} = \frac{D_{eq}}{D_{eq}^{(elastic)}} \quad (15)$$

and this quantity is shown in Fig. 9 as a function of the applied shear stress. Once the plastic buckling stress is known, the effective stiffness parameter can be calculated from Fig. 9, after which Eq. (5) can be used to check whether an overall or local buckling mode occurs. Note that the quantity $\mu_F^{(elastic)} / \mu_F$ is actually equal to the plasticity correction factor η , which can be derived from Eqs. (1) and (13).

As an alternative procedure to calculate the inelastic shear buckling stress, the curves in Fig. 9 can be used in conjunction with those in Fig. 3. The value of the effective μ_F is first calculated from Fig. 9 at a currently applied shear stress, after which the shear buckling coefficient K_s can be obtained from Fig. 3, and the inelastic shear buckling stress can be calculated from Eq. (1) using the current value of D_{eq} . Since the values of μ_F and D_{eq} are dependent on the shear stress, this particular approach requires an iterative procedure.

Fig. 8: Plasticity correction factors for Glare 3 panels as a function of elastic shear buckling stress for different values of the metal volume fraction.

Fig. 9: Curves relating the effective to the elastic stiffness parameter as a function of the applied shear stress for Glare 3 panels.

DISCUSSION

When the inelastic shear buckling stress of both aluminium and Glare panels is calculated with the assumption of isotropic material properties, it was shown for specific examples that the results are about 6% unconservative with respect to the orthotropic solutions. While Glare is, by its nature, an orthotropic material due to the arrangement of the glass fibres, aluminium behaves orthotropically in the plastic region due to a change of the in-plane stiffness matrix. The results from the isotropic approach were calculated using previously derived elastic buckling curves for stiffened shear panels, while the fully orthotropic analysis was performed using accurate—thus relatively large—FEM models. Since the calculation procedure requires a lot of small load increments, at each of which a buckling analysis must be performed, the latter process requires a lot of computing time. This is

contrary to the isotropic method, where a single buckling solution is “readily available” and the calculation of the inelastic shear buckling stress is done in a matter of seconds. Plasticity correction factors, which are commonly used for design purposes, were calculated for both aluminium and Glare using the isotropic approach, and they were shown to be slightly unconservative with respect to the orthotropic solution. Furthermore, it was found that the correction factors are independent of the actual panel configuration and only a function of the elastic buckling stress. Since the elasto-plastic buckling behaviour of Glare is governed by the aluminium content, the plasticity correction factors are different for different Glare configurations. Therefore, plasticity correction factors were generated as a function of the elastic shear buckling stress for Glare configurations with varying aluminium content. These results can be conveniently used as design curves with respect to inelastic shear buckling.

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